

Kristianstad University CoARA Action Plan

Kristianstad University is located in south Sweden and hosts around 14,000 students and employs approximately 500 staff members. The university emphasizes applied research, often collaborating with local and regional industries to enhance its research impact and relevance. This approach supports a strong integration between education, research, and real-world application, making it a dynamic center for academic and professional development.

Kristianstad University (HKR) emphasizes the core values of openness, commitment and closeness, together with curiosity and respect. They highlight the importance of being an open and transparent institution, encouraging a curious approach towards learning and research, and fostering close and respectful relationships among students, faculty, and staff. These guiding principles shape the university's culture and its interactions both internally and with the wider community.

HKR's values resonate with CoARA's objectives to promote transparency and fairness in research assessment. By adopting CoARA's principles, HKR can further commit to these values in its research practices.

Kristianstad University signed CoARA in March 2023 and is part of the CoARA working group TIER, which focuses on transparency, Inclusiveness, Engagement, and Responsibility in research assessment. This also reflects the focus of HKR's role in our European University Alliance, COLOURS, where HKR is head of the Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) work package.

Strategy

Kristianstad university has by tradition a heavy focus on teaching, with career-oriented programs catering to regional educational needs. As a counter to HKR's education-heavy history, the university is now working on enhancing its research capabilities and is in a dynamic, strategic development phase aimed at boosting research activities and advancing research careers. Thus, the strategy to implement CoARA will largely involve integrating it into HKR's ongoing efforts to develop and expand its research focus, rather than altering an existing

framework. In short, a key priority and challenge for HKR is to strengthen and broaden its research focus across the organization, with CoARA playing a vital role in its successful implementation.

In line with this strategic shift, HKR's ongoing work with CoARA will be evaluated as part of a new research quality mapping routine, scheduled for introduction in 2025 and beyond. Communication efforts and other activities will be conducted within the organisations existing platforms and networks. Moreover, to further support this development, HKR is currently in the process of preparing an application to the HR Excellence in Research Award based on the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R). This step will reinforce the university's dedication to ensuring that recruitment and working conditions for researchers are attractive, fair, and transparent, aligning with HKR's core values.

Prioritized areas

- **Skills Development for Early Career Researchers**
- **Open Science** (e.g., open access to publications, data sharing, and other open research practices)
- **Acknowledge More Varied Research Outputs** (recognizing a broader spectrum of research outputs, including non-traditional academic contributions)
- **Value Research Contributions Outside Academia**, such as collaboration projects and the societal impact of research

We will prioritize recognizing collaborative practices and the societal impact of research, broadening the criteria for valuing contributions beyond academia, including non-traditional research outputs. Additionally, we will enhance our efforts in capacity building for early-career researchers and advance our open science initiatives. Our priority areas and objectives will evolve over time, informed by the progress of the HKR working group, the HRS4R work process, and synergies with the COLOURS alliance project. This development will also be supported by the exchange of best practices and insights, facilitated by the recently launched Swedish National Chapter.

The implementation of CoARA at HKR will be led by a dedicated Working Group (WG), which will operate as a subgroup within the existing HRS4R Working Group and Steering Board structure. This approach leverages the significant overlap in their focus areas, ensuring a coordinated and comprehensive

strategy. The WG will engage with the broader research community at HKR through workshops and other activities, gathering valuable input to guide the university's commitment to CoARA. Leadership of this initiative will be provided by the vice rector for research, who will report directly to the Steering Board, reflecting the university's senior management's commitment to these efforts.

Planned activities

1. Raise awareness about CoARA and the advancement of assessment of research and researchers that its core principles communicate.
 - a. Communication plan.
2. Review how HKR's research assessment practices align with CoARA's principles and core commitments through...
 - a. Workshops with researchers. Vice rector for research with the research platform leaders and the research environment leaders.
 - b. Assessment of the university's current functions' alignment with CoARA to be summarized in a report, partly supported by the outcome of the HR Excellence in Research Award GAP-analysis.
3. Whenever appropriate, actively consider and incorporate the CoARA principles in the development of HKR's research activities and ambitions.
4. Engage in activities, events and knowledge sharing efforts via the Swedish National Chapter.
5. Participate in the TIER Working Group according to institutional capacity.

The Kristianstad University CoARA Action Plan will be considered an open document and will develop and expand with time.

Kristianstad University assessment reform roadmap 2023-2028

2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
<i>Signing CoARA</i>	<i>Joining WG TIER</i>	<i>When appropriate, formulate assessment tools, procedures,</i>	<i>When appropriate, formulate assessment tools, procedures,</i>	<i>When appropriate, formulate assessment tools, procedures,</i>	<i>Report progress</i>

		<i>and criteria consistent with the core commitments</i>	<i>and criteria consistent with the core commitments</i>	<i>and criteria consistent with the core commitments</i>	
<i>Highlighting and promoting CoARA internally</i>	<i>Establishing a CoARA working group at HKR</i>				
<i>Considering suitable WG to join</i>	<i>Do a review of how HKRs practices align with CoARA's core principles</i>	<i>Use existing platforms and HKR's internal and external websites to share updates on progress</i>	<i>Use existing platforms and HKR's internal and external websites to share updates on progress</i>	<i>Use existing platforms and HKR's internal and external websites to share updates on progress</i>	
	<i>Introduction meeting for the Swedish National Chapter</i>	<i>Leverage appropriate networks to exchange experience and best practice</i>	<i>Leverage appropriate networks to exchange experience and best practice</i>	<i>Leverage appropriate networks to exchange experience and best practice</i>	
	<i>Hand in Action Plan</i>				